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E-driver, what about your charging infrastructure? A large-scale European study on charging habits, perceptions, concerns and expectations

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Abstract

1. Overview and motivation

During the last years, the adoption of the electric vehicle (EV) technology has been accelerating. This adoption resulted last year in a combined market share for battery electric vehicles (BEVs) and plug-in electric vehicles (PHEVs) of 10% in Europe (EAFO, 2021). This trend is also visible for light electric vehicles (LEVs), for which almost 250.000 new vehicles were registered in the same year across the European Union member states. This translates in a need for more infrastructure, but also on that front an extension of the existing network is observed with approximately 200.000 regular charging points (< 22 kW) and 25.000 fast charging points (>22 kW) installed in the union (EAFO, 2021). Since the EV uptake and charging infrastructure roll out are accelerating, it is the right time to assess the existing charging infrastructure and reflect on possible improvements.

eCharge4Drivers is an H2020 project running from June 2020 to May 2024 and deployed by a consortium of 32 partners. Charging an electric vehicle (EV) is still not as convenient as refuelling a conventional vehicle, potentially posing a barrier to increase the market uptake of EVs. eCharge4Drivers works to substantially improve the EV charging experience within cities and for long trips. The project develops and demonstrates user-friendly charging stations and innovative charging solutions as well as smart charging services for the users.

In this paper we report on the a priori users' concerns and expectations survey conducted in the winter of 2020-2021. Based on a large-scale survey with almost 3,000 valid responses across the 10 project demonstration areas, the current users' charging habits, perceptions, concerns and expectations were measured; the users' mobility and parking habits surveyed as well as factors influencing users' decision making regarding charging an EV.

2. Methodology, results and main contributions

The emphasis of the survey's questions for EV-users was on the following topics: their use of the vehicle, their motives, their parking behaviour, their charging behaviour, the quality of their experience with existing public charging infrastructure, their acceptance of charging options tested in later phases of the project and app-based services. The questions were mainly based on existing scientific frameworks such as the CIS (Charging Infrastructure Satisfaction)-diagnostic (for the quality of experience regarding existing charging infrastructure) from Vanhaverbeke et al. (2018) and Nuytens et al. (2020), and the UTAUT (Unified Theory for Acceptance and Use of Technology) model (for the acceptance of smart charging, fast charging, battery swapping, mobile charging services and user friendly charging stations) from Venkatesh, Thong & Xu (2012). The development of the survey was an iterative process involving the demonstration areas for feedback and piloting of the survey. The final survey was translated to the local language(s) of all demonstration areas to accommodate the respondents. The survey

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was launched on the 23rd of November 2020 and stayed online and available for respondents until the 8th of March 2021. In total 4.703 respondents participated in the survey, of which 2.966 respondents were eligible for analysis after data cleaning.

The majority of the respondents were male and highly educated. On average 63% of the EV drivers have a private vehicle and 32% a company car. The reasons for choosing an EV are primarily environmental friendliness, energy efficiency and low operating and maintenance costs. The vehicle kilometres travelled for a day vary between 30 in Berlin up to 148 in Turkey, with an average of 81 across the demonstration areas. Between 73% and 88% of the respondents have access to a private garage or driveway at home, and the vehicle is parked there approximately 12 hours, with variation between 8 and 14 hours.

EV drivers plan their charging activity according to the anticipation on the next trip, the state-of-charge below a certain level and when there is a possibility to charge. There is little variation in these reasons across the different demonstration areas. The usage of apps by EV users varies between 30% in Greece up to 80% in Northern Italy. Overall, the satisfaction of EV drivers with the eMSP/CPO scores high: on average 5,5 out of 7. This is a score of 8/10 overall. There is quite some variation though, with scores ranging between 3,83 and 6,36. It is noteworthy that two dimensions related to issues during a charging experience score lowest: compensation with an average of 3,32 out of 7 and contact, with an average of 4,02. When asked about an ideal charging session, the characteristics are commonly shared across the demonstration areas: on top, there is a charging pass that works immediately, next comes short connection and waiting time.

3. Conclusion and future works

The majority of the surveyed EV drivers charge at home, however also the public charging infrastructure is crucial. Overall, EV drivers give their eMSP/CPO a score on satisfaction of 8/10. Problem resolution, interoperability and availability of the charging systems are the main concerns of EV drivers.

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